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Master in Data Management
and Curation

Extending NOMAD schemas for the UMIL NFFFA-DI Theory & Simulation Installation, with a focus on the Yambo code

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Trieste, May 28th, 2025

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Outline

1. Introduction and Motivation
2. Our project (NFFA-DI, the UMIL Theo&Sim lab, NOMAD and our codes)
3. Strategy (NOMAD and our codes: functionalities and issues → Objectives)
4. Results
5. Conclusions and Perspectives

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1 Introduction and Motivation

All you need is ...

* **Data**

- * data as a main “ingredient” of scientific research
- * huge amounts of data and how to store / organize / extract the maximum possible information

Data-driven
(.....)

**Data
scientist**

**Data
mining**

**Big
data**

**Data
management**

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1 Introduction and Motivation

All you need is ...

* Data

* **Quality data**
(in particular for **AI / ML**)

R. Natras and M. Schmidt CDCEO 2021:
1st Workshop on ComplexData Challenges
in Earth Observation, November 1, 2021,
Virtual Event, QLD, Australia (2021) .

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1 Introduction and Motivation

All you need is ...

- * Data
- * Quality data
- * **FAIR data**

Open Science (OS): A set of values, principles, and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone, for the benefit of the whole humanity

Pillars of Open Science:

- *Open scientific knowledge*
- *Open science infrastructure*
- Open engagement of societal actors
- Open dialogue with other knowledge systems

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.2021. CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO license.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>
UNESCO Open Science Toolkit. 2023. CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO license.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000387983>

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1 Introduction and Motivation

All you need is ...

- * Data
- * Quality data
- * **FAIR data**

*As open as possible,
As closed as necessary*

- 1. Findable** – Easy to find by both humans *and computer systems* thanks to rich metadata and unique persistent identifiers
- 2. Accessible** – Stored for easy access and downloading
- 3. Interoperable** – Ready to be combined with other datasets by humans *and computer systems*
- 4. Re-usable** – Ready for reuse thanks to detailed, accurate documentation and clear usage license

(see e.g. Skills4EOSC, "Open Science and evidence-informed decision making" courses, <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>)

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1 Introduction and Motivation

FAIR (and in particular *Interoperability*)
In Computational Material Science

All you need is ...

- * Data
- * Quality data
- * FAIR data

<https://www.max-centre.eu>

<https://www.mgi.gov>

*Several platforms / projects,
offering: running simulations,
Data upload / publishing
/ search / analysis...,
training, code optimization...*

<https://next-gen.materialsproject.org>

<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab>

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2.1 The NFFA-DI project

NANOSCIENCE FOUNDRIES AND FINE ANALYSIS - DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

NFFA-DI: A DISTRIBUTED ITALIAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE INTEGRATING STATE OF THE ART INSTRUMENTATION, COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES AND FAIR-BY-DESIGN APPROACH

The NFFA upgrade proposal for a Full-Spectrum Italian Research Infrastructure for nanoscience and nanotechnology (PNRR funded)

- 4 Leading Italian research institutions as partners
- 11 Operational units
- 5 Distributed installations
- > 40 Scientific techniques
- > 70 Instruments available to external users
- > 50 Researchers involved in the infrastructure

FUNDED BY PNRR

~ 34 M€

2023-2025

Finanziato dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO

<https://nffa-di.it>

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2.2 The UMIL Theory&Simulation lab: Computational materials science

Operative Unit	Experimental technique
UniMi-Fisica	AFM
	CBD - Cluster Beam Deposition
	Direct-laser-writing
	Electron-Ion-Coincidence
	IR-Spectroscopy
	Mass-Spectroscopy
	RAMAN
	Scanning Field Emission Microscopy
	SEM
	STM
	Theory-and-simulation
	XPS

C. Zagni, F. Bazzocchi,
WP3 visit @UMIL, 15.04.24

nffa-di

About us | Our offer | Get access | Outcomes | News

Theory & Simulation

THEO & SIM

TP
TRANSPORT PROPERTIES

AMM
ATOMS AND MOLECULES IN MOTION

ESP
EXCITED-STATE PROPERTIES

SGSEP
Structural and ground-state electronic

MULTI-SCALE
MULTI-SCALE PROCESS SIMULATION

tallation-10094

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2.2 The UMIL Theory&Simulation lab: Computational materials science

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	RAMAN
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	SEM
	STM
	Theory-and-simulation
XPS	

C. Zagni, F. Bazzocchi,
WP3 visit @UMIL, 15.04.24

Instrument = Simulation code	Technique = Computational method
QE	SGSEP (Structural and ground state electronic properties)
	MP (Magnetic properties)
Siesta	SGSEP (Structural and ground state electronic properties)
	MP (Magnetic properties)
Yambo	ESP (Excited state properties)
Transiesta	TP (Transport properties)
LAMMPS	AMM (Atoms and Molecules in Motion)

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Data producers

2.3 NOMAD and our codes

NOMAD → see next slides

(from Fig. 1 of NFFA-DI deliverable D1.2)

* NOMAD (data)
* Zenodo etc (publications etc)

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2.3 NOMAD and our codes

NOMAD (<https://nomad-lab.eu>)

* **Data Repository** chosen by the *NFFA-DI* project for the upload, storage and publishing of its research data in a **structured** way according to the **FAIR principles**

* a free and open source web-based **repository**, developed by the german *FAIRmat* consortium, for **FAIR Research Data Management in materials science** (both computational and experimental)

* *NOMAD was originally born for computational data*

* *we are a computational lab*

* *the simulation codes we offer are NOMAD-supported*

But... (see later)

NOMAD SOLUTIONS ▾ LEARN ▾ GET INVOLVED ▾ ABOUT ▾ OPEN NOMAD

NOMAD

Materials science data managed and shared

NOMAD lets you manage and share your materials science data in a way that makes it truly useful to you, your group, and the community. **Free and open source.**

Open NOMAD →

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2.3 NOMAD and our codes

NOMAD (<https://nomad-lab.eu>)

* hierarchical structure:

sections, subsections...

* data upload / publishing

/ search / visualization / analysis

* **Oasis** = local NOMAD instance

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2.3 NOMAD and our codes

NOMAD (<https://nomad-lab.eu>)

* hierarchical structure:

sections, subsections...

* data upload / publishing

/ search / visualization / analysis

* **Oasis** = local NOMAD instance

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3.1 Strategy: NOMAD and our codes: Functionalities and issues

QuantumEspresso:

- NOMAD does not produce band structure plots for QE
- NOMAD considers as QE mainfiles the *.out files produced by the pw.x executable only, thus excluding the outputs of pp.x postprocessing runs

Yambo:

- NOMAD does not write / display **chemical composition, cell parameters, atom positions**
- NOMAD does not plot **spectra**
- NOMAD yields error messages on our test upload of Yambo GW data

Siesta:

- NOMAD does not plot band structures and density of states (DOS)
- NOMAD fails in parsing the "xcauthor" string (related to the name of the chosen exchange-correlation [XC] functional)

LAMMPS:

- NOMAD considers both log.* files and *.out files as LAMMPS mainfiles. The *.out file generally contains less info than the log.* one: this can result in entries lacking some information on the system, when based on a *.out file as mainfile
- cell parameters, MD trajectory etc are displayed / plotted only in some cases (by inspecting already present uploads and performing uploads of our data)

Output of dedicated
**NOMAD dissemination
meetings /hands-on
sessions** ("xxx-code
on NOMAD") I have
organized for colleagues

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3.2 My MDMC objectives

- * Data Management Plans (**DMP**) and Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms
- * install an **Oasis** (= a local NOMAD instance) → both for testing our parser implementations and for subsequent use as data repository for UMIL Theo&Sim research data

NOMAD and our codes:

- Plotting QE band structures
- Solving the NOMAD error on Yambo GW files
- Reporting and displaying Yambo **cell parameters, atom coords, chemical composition**
- Plotting Yambo **spectra**
- Reporting / displaying at least some of the relevant physical quantities from Siesta runs

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4.1.a Data Management Plans

NFFA-DI: **Hierarchical** organization of DMPs:

* **Project DMP**: data management guidelines for the whole project

* **Lab DMPs**: specific data management strategies for a specific instrument/technique combination (n. "labs" = n. instrum-technique combin > n. OUs)

* **Proposal DMP**: written by the PIs of approved NFFA-DI user projects

Each level **inherits** from the higher levels
→ coherence; ease of use

(M. de Luca, MDMC course slides)

- DMPs are living documents

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4.1.a Data Management Plans

UMIL Theo&Sim lab:

Specificities:

- * several entries in the std DMP template do not apply to computational techniques
- * all the codes we offer are **open source**
→ no proprietary formats; text or hdf5
- * will use **NOMAD** as Data Repository already at lab level
- * code/technique-dependent: Instrum Scientist, Data size, technique name and description

Strategy:

- 1) start from preliminary DMPs contained in the D5.3 NFFA-DI Deliverable (based on the information we had put in the NFFA-DI catalog)
- 2) check for changes/updates
- 3) align DMPs / NFFA-DI catalog of techniques (<https://nffa-di.it/en/our-offer/#installation-10104>)

Name

DMP_UMI_LAMMPS_AMM_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_QE_MP_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_QE_SGSEP_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_SIESTA_MP_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_SIESTA_SGSEP_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_TRANSIESTA_TP_feb25.docx
DMP_UMI_YAMBO_ESP_feb25.docx

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4.1.b Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms

NFFA-DI Remote Access policy: (see deliverable D6.1)

* ensure the possibility for external users of having remote access to NFFA-DI facilities within their user projects without the need of physically travelling to the chosen NFFA-DI OU

* several different levels and types of Remote Access to a research infrastructure:

- connecting to the computers at the OU labs through ssh, ftp, vpn etc

- remote access to experimental instruments

full and autonomous remote access, including direct control of the instrument (challenging due to the specificity of the instrumentation available at NFFA-DI OUs and the expertise required for its use)

Interactive Remote Access (IRA):
remote connection of the external user with the on-site operator who directly operates the instrumentation

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4.1.b Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms

UMIL Theo&Sim lab:

- * computational lab: techniques = comput. methods; instruments = codes
- * open source codes
- * often using external HPC facilities (e.g. CINECA)
- * (from NFFA.eu experience): users = experimentalists, generally with no experience in simulations

--> (At a difference with experimental NFFA-DI OUs/labs):

we are *mainly* offering:

- * our expertise - as users and in some cases also developers – in a set of computational material science methods and simulation codes
- * ~~access to simulation codes, or to our computational resources~~

For UMIL Theo&Sim: remote access / remote control: Yes; protocol: ssh

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4.2 NOMAD Oasis

Oasis = a local instance of NOMAD

- same functionalities as NOMAD
- local research data management according to the FAIR principles
- possibility of preparing data for subsequent upload and publishing on the general NOMAD platform
- locally implement new functionalities tailored to a lab's specific needs

NOMAD

Oasis

Basic infra

1. Ensure you have [docker](#) installed. Docker nowadays comes with `docker compose` built in. Prior, you needed to install the stand-alone [docker-compose](#).
2. Install [uv](#) (v0.5.14 and above). `uv` is required to manage your development environment. It's recommended to use the standalone installer or perform a global installation. (`brew install uv` on macOS or `dnf install uv` on Fedora).
3. Install [node.js](#) (v20) and [yarn](#)(v1.22). We will use it to setup the GUI.
4. For Windows users, `nomad-lab` processing doesn't work natively on the platform. We highly recommend using the [Devcontainer](#) plugin in VSCode to run the repository within a container, or alternatively, using [Windows Subsystem for Linux](#) (WSL) to run the project.
5. Clone the forked repository.

<https://github.com/FAIRmat-NFDI/nomad-distro-dev>

-
- installed a “personal” Oasis on my work pc
 - used it for all the following development work on NOMAD parsers
 - IT team has installed a UMIL Theo&Sim group Oasis on a dedicated Virtual Machine; still to be finalized (create users, how to make updates..)

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4.3 NOMAD: QE band structure plotting

Example from other codes: *FHaims*, ZnSe
(entry ID: rQn4Umvd5uaEljmudVbl6asU3_FK)

Electronic properties

Band structure

Density of states

Brillouin zone

Band gaps

Ch.	Value (eV)	Type
0	1.251	direct

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4.3 NOMAD: QE band structure plotting

Example from other codes: *FHlaims*, ZnSe
(entry ID: rQn4Umvd5uaEljmudVbl6asU3_FK)

The screenshot displays the NOMAD web interface with the following structure:

- Entry** (section [EntryArchive](#))
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - results**
 - metadata
 - workflow2
 - run
 - REFERENCED BY [closed](#)
- Results** (section [Results](#))
 - sub section [results](#)
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - material
 - method
 - properties**
 - REFERENCED BY [closed](#)
- Properties** (section [Properties](#))
 - sub section [properties](#)
 - QUANTITIES
 - n calculations = 1
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - electronic**
 - REFERENCED BY [closed](#)
- Electronic Properties** (section [ElectronicProperties](#))
 - sub section [electronic](#)
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - band gap
 - band structure electronic**
 - REFERENCED BY [closed](#)
- Band Structure Electronic** (section [BandStructureElectronic](#))
 - sub section [band_structure_electronic](#)
 - QUANTITIES
 - spin polarized = false
 - reciprocal cell = *reference ...*
 - energy fermi = -5.62002 eV
 - ▼ **segment**
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - band gap
 - REFERENCED BY [closed](#)

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4.3 NOMAD: QE band structure plotting

QuantumEspresso: Our data (test, unpublished):
band str dataset → no band str parsed/plotted

Material

ORIGINAL Si

CONVENTIONAL CELL
bulk

Description:
A representative system chosen from the original simulation.

COMPOSITION		CELL
Chemical formula hill	Si ₂	Chemical formula IUPAC
Chemical formula IUPAC	Si	Label
Structural type	unavailable	Material id
Label	original	unavailable
Elements	N elements	N atoms
Si	1 (unary)	2

Entry section EntryArchive

SUB SECTIONS

- results
- metadata
- workflow2
- run

REFERENCED BY closed

Results section Results

sub section results

SUB SECTIONS

- material
- method
- properties

REFERENCED BY closed

Properties section Properties

sub section properties

QUANTITIES

n calculations = 1

REFERENCED BY closed

Entry References

Referencing the following entries

Not referencing other entries.

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4.3 NOMAD: QE band structure plotting

Band structures:

rather different formats for different codes

..and sometimes even within a single code... e.g. QuantumEspresso

```

&plot nbnd= 8, nks= 36 /
  0.500000 0.500000 0.500000
-3.418 -0.822 5.029 5.029 7.814 9.597 9.597 13.838
  0.400000 0.400000 0.400000
-3.891 -0.102 5.102 5.102 7.900 9.679 9.679 13.959
  0.300000 0.300000 0.300000
-4.659 1.404 5.319 5.319 8.138 9.803 9.803 13.845
  0.200000 0.200000 0.200000
-5.285 3.222 5.660 5.660 8.504 9.636 9.636 12.333
  0.100000 0.100000 0.100000
-5.678 5.104 6.050 6.050 8.848 9.120 9.120 10.612
  0.000000 0.000000 0.000000
-5.810 6.255 6.255 6.255 8.822 8.822 8.822 9.723
  0.000000 0.000000 0.100000
-5.767 5.981 6.072 6.072 8.710 9.057 9.057 9.984
  0.000000 0.000000 0.200000

```

```

0.1732 -3.0510
0.3464 -4.6593
0.5196 -5.2849
0.6928 -5.6783
0.8660 -5.8099
0.9660 -5.7668
(.....)
3.7146 -4.4382
3.8560 -5.0244
3.9974 -5.4577
4.1388 -5.7218
4.2802 -5.8099

0.0000 -0.8220
0.1732 -0.1018
0.3464 1.4042
0.5196 3.2219
0.6928 5.1037
0.8660 6.2549

```


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4.4 NOMAD: Yambo GW error

Our data: Yambo GW, FePc → (no plots and) **1 error**

The screenshot displays four panels from the NOMAD interface:

- Entry**: section `EntryArchive`. SUB SECTIONS: `metadata` (circled in green), `run` (circled in blue). REFERENCED BY: `closed`.
- Run**: section `Run`. sub section `run`. SUB SECTIONS: `program`, `time run`, `method` (0, 1, 2, 3), `calculation` (0, 1). REFERENCED BY: `not referenced by other entries`.
- Calculation**: section `Calculation`. sub section `calculation`. SUB SECTIONS: `energy` (circled in blue). REFERENCED BY: `not referenced by other entries`.
- Energy**: section `Energy`. sub section `energy`. QUANTITIES: `fermi = -3.58793 eV`, `highest occupied = 0 eV`, `lowest unoccupied = 0 eV`. REFERENCED BY: `closed`.

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4.4 NOMAD: Yambo GW error

Our data: Yambo GW, FePc → (no plots and) **1 error**

GW ("QP") corrections

Entry section EntryArchive

SUB SECTIONS

- metadata
- run**

REFERENCED BY closed

Run section Run

sub section run

SUB SECTIONS

- program
- time run
- method
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3
- calculation
 - 0**
 - 1

REFERENCED BY

not referenced by other entries

Corrections @ K [1] : [eV]

<1(up) nLXC 1(up)> = -60.58015	-0.202615E-8	<1(up) LXC 1(up)> = -44.44817	-0.50654E-09
<1(dn) nLXC 1(dn)> = -55.81659	0.43636E-09	<1(dn) LXC 1(dn)> = -41.75391	0.10909E-09
<2(up) nLXC 2(up)> = -54.54885	0.16246E-09	<2(up) LXC 2(up)> = -40.88595	0.40615E-10
<2(dn) nLXC 2(dn)> = -49.25706	-0.40026E-09	<2(dn) LXC 2(dn)> = -38.51508	-0.10007E-09
<3(up) nLXC 3(up)> = -52.97009	0.88651E-09	<3(up) LXC 3(up)> = -40.55759	0.22163E-09
<3(dn) nLXC 3(dn)> = -46.71142	-0.192216E-8	<3(dn) LXC 3(dn)> = -37.16329	-0.48054E-09
<4(up) nLXC 4(up)> = -52.20274	0.18892E-09	<4(up) LXC 4(up)> = -40.18005	0.47230E-10
<4(dn) nLXC 4(dn)> = -45.49643	-0.92513E-10	<4(dn) LXC 4(dn)> = -36.73127	-0.23128E-10
<5(up) nLXC 5(up)> = -28.31205	-0.92218E-10	<5(up) LXC 5(up)> = -20.36825	-0.23054E-10
<5(dn) nLXC 5(dn)> = -28.33789	-0.551516E-8	<5(dn) LXC 5(dn)> = -20.38125	-0.137879E-8
<6(up) nLXC 6(up)> = -28.22698	-0.175176E-8	<6(up) LXC 6(up)> = -20.39973	-0.43794E-09
<6(dn) nLXC 6(dn)> = -28.26038	-0.73314E-09	<6(dn) LXC 6(dn)> = -20.41907	-0.18328E-09

```

"step" : string "electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point"
"logger" : string "nomad.processing"
"exception" :
string "Traceback (most recent call last): File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/nomad/processing/data.py",
line 1508, in parsing parser.parse( File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/nomad/parsing/parser.py", line
461, in parse self.mainfile_parser.parse(mainfile, archive, logger) File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-
packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 894, in parse parse_module(module) File
"/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 880, in parse_module
self.parse_local_xc_nonlocal_fock(module) File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-
packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 794, in parse_local_xc_nonlocal_fock sx, vxc =
np.transpose([c.band for c in source.corrections]) ^^^^^^^^^ ValueError: not enough values to unpack (expected 2, got
1)"
"timestamp" : string "2025-05-22 10:04:51"
"level" : string "ERROR"

```


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4.4 NOMAD: Yambo GW error

Our data: Yambo GW, FePc → (no plots and) **1 error**

```
"step" : string "electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point"
"logger" : string "nomad.processing"
"exception" :
string "Traceback (most recent call last): File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/nomad/processing/data.py",
line 1508, in parsing parser.parse( File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/nomad/parsing/parser.py", line
461, in parse self.mainfile_parser.parse(mainfile, archive, logger) File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-
packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 894, in parse parse_module(module) File
"/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 880, in parse_module
self.parse_local_xc_nonlocal_fock(module) File "/opt/venv/lib/python3.12/site-
packages/electronicparsers/yambo/parser.py", line 794, in parse_local_xc_nonlocal_fock sx, vxc =
np.transpose([c.band for c in source.corrections]) ^^^^^^^^^ ValueError: not enough values to unpack (expected 2, got
1)"
```

```
"t-----" : string "2025-07-23 10:04:53"
"l
Corrections @ K [1] : [eV]
<1(up)|nLXC|1(up)> = -60.58015 -0.202615E-8 <1(up)|LXC|1(up)> = -44.44817 -0.50654E-09
<1(dn)|nLXC|1(dn)> = -55.81659 0.43636E-09 <1(dn)|LXC|1(dn)> = -41.75391 0.10909E-09
<2(up)|nLXC|2(up)> = -54.54885 0.16246E-09 <2(up)|LXC|2(up)> = -40.88595 0.40615E-10
<2(dn)|nLXC|2(dn)> = -49.25706 -0.40026E-09 <2(dn)|LXC|2(dn)> = -38.51508 -0.10007E-09
<3(up)|nLXC|3(up)> = -52.97009 0.88651E-09 <3(up)|LXC|3(up)> = -40.55759 0.22163E-09
<3(dn)|nLXC|3(dn)> = -46.71142 -0.192216E-8 <3(dn)|LXC|3(dn)> = -37.16329 -0.48054E-09
<4(up)|nLXC|4(up)> = -52.20274 0.18892E-09 <4(up)|LXC|4(up)> = -40.18005 0.47230E-10
<4(dn)|nLXC|4(dn)> = -45.49643 -0.92513E-10 <4(dn)|LXC|4(dn)> = -36.73127 -0.23128E-10
<5(up)|nLXC|5(up)> = -28.31205 -0.92218E-10 <5(up)|LXC|5(up)> = -20.36825 -0.23054E-10
<5(dn)|nLXC|5(dn)> = -28.33789 -0.551516E-8 <5(dn)|LXC|5(dn)> = -20.38125 -0.137879E-8
<6(up)|nLXC|6(up)> = -28.22698 -0.175176E-8 <6(up)|LXC|6(up)> = -20.39973 -0.43794E-09
<6(dn)|nLXC|6(dn)> = -28.26038 -0.73314E-09 <6(dn)|LXC|6(dn)> = -20.41907 -0.18328E-09
```

* discussed on the NOMAD Discord:
<https://discord.com/channels/1201445470485106719/1201454263260413992/threads/1348983787018653777>

* **A. N. Ladines** (FAIRmat team) working on it: the error was due to neglecting the possibility of having two separate spin channels (spin polarized systems)

* A.N.L. has written a fix for this → we have tested it → no error

.....then it would be nice to plot e.g. GW-corrected band structures vs IP band str.....

→ possible future task

GW vs DFT

J. Cervantes-Villanueva et al., Phys. Rev. **B 109**, 155133 (2023). Bulk Bil₃

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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters

(with Hajar Belgroun,
undergraduate
internship student)

Our upload: **R-methyloxirane** molecule

OVERVIEW page: no info on
chemical composition, cell parameters etc

Entry files

folder

- o-R_methylox_TDLDA.alpha_q1_slepc_alda_bse
- r-R_methylox_TDLDA_rim_cut_optics_bss... electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point
- r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

INFO: electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point | normalizer completed successfully olteni

INFO: electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point | normalizer executed sets

WARNING: electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point | no "representative" section system found

INFO: electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point | normalizer completed successfully

INFO: electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point | normalizer executed

FILES

Metadata

Workflow name
SinglePoint
Program version
5.1.0 Revision 19888
Program name
YAMBO
Entry type
YAMBO SinglePoint
Entry name
YAMBO SinglePoint simulation

Comment
no comment

References

Material

Composition	
Chemical formula IUPAC <i>unavailable</i>	Chemical formula reduced <i>unavailable</i>
Chemical formula hill <i>unavailable</i>	Chemical formula descriptive <i>unavailable</i>
Elements <i>unavailable</i>	N elements 0

Workflow Graph

No task to show

...Similar behaviour for existing Yambo uploads
from other authors on the general NOMAD

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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters

NOMAD Yambo test folder: hBN

→ Info on chemical composition, cell parameters etc is parsed, atoms in the cell are shown

Entry files

folder

10b_1Ry

SAVE

r-10b_1Ry_HF_and_locXC_gw0_em1d_ppa electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

COMPOSITION

CELL

A	B	C
2.79 Å	2.161 Å	6.444 Å
Alpha	Beta	Gamma
90 °	90 °	116.565 °
Volume	Mass density	Atomic density
34.755 Å ³	2.372e-27 kg / Å ³	0.115 Å ⁻³

Material

ORIGINAL

Description:

A representative system chosen from the original simulation.

COMPOSITION

CELL

Chemical formula hill B2N2	Chemical formula IUPAC BN	
Structural type <i>unavailable</i>	Label original	Material id <i>unavailable</i>
Elements B, N	N elements 2 (binary)	N atoms 4

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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters

NOMAD Yambo test folder: hBN
→ Info on chemical composition,
cell parameters etc is parsed

Entry files

folder

10b_1Ry

SAVE

r-10b_1Ry_HF_and_locXC_gw0_em1d_ppa electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

**!SAVE/ns.db is needed
for NOMAD to parse
chemical composition,
cell params etc**

Material

ORIGINAL

Description:

A representative system chosen from
the original simulation.

COMPOSITION

CELL

Chemical formula hill

B2N2

Chemical formula IUPAC

BN

Structural type

unavailable

Label

original

Material id

unavailable

Elements

B, N

N elements

2 (binary)

N atoms

4

COMPOSITION

CELL

A	B	C
2.79 Å	2.161 Å	6.444 Å
Alpha	Beta	Gamma
90 °	90 °	116.565 °
Volume	Mass density	Atomic density
34.755 Å ³	2.372e-27 kg / Å ³	0.115 Å ⁻³

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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters

NOMAD Yambo test folder: hBN
→ Info on chemical composition,
cell parameters etc is parsed

Entry files
folder

- 10b_1Ry
- SAVE**
- r-10b_1Ry_HF_and_locXC_gw0_em1d_ppa electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point
- r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

**!SAVE/ns.db is needed
for NOMAD to parse
chemical composition,
cell params etc**

...not enough documented in the
README etc

→ Based on our feedback,
FAIRmat team have indicated this
In the **“issues”** page:
[https://github.com/nomad-coe/
electronic-parsers/issues](https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/issues)

COMPOSITION

CELL

A	B	C
2.79 Å	2.161 Å	6.444 Å
Alpha	Beta	Gamma
90 °	90 °	116.565 °
Volume	Mass density	Atomic density
34.755 Å ³	2.372e-27 kg / Å ³	0.115 Å ⁻³

Entry files

folder

- 10b_1Ry
- SAVE**
- r-10b_1Ry_HF_and_locXC_gw0_em1d_ppa electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point
- r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point

SAVE folder

- ns.db1

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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters: Further issues...

* A different system
(our data): CH_4

* /SAVE/ns.db present

Error: mismatch bw *n. of atom coordinates*
and *n. of atoms*

DATA LOGS

System → <> Atoms → <>

section System Atoms

sub section system atoms

QUANTITIES

is representative = true

chemical composition = HHHHC

chemical composition hill = CH₄

chemical composition reduced = CH₄

SUB SECTIONS

atoms

REFERENCED BY closed

REFERENCED BY closed

Could not load structure.

QUANTITIES

species = 5 vector

labels = 5 list

positions = 8 x 3 matrix

lattice vectors = 3 x 3 matrix

periodic = 3 list

```
ERROR: electronicparsers.yambo_parser_entry_point | len of atom position does not match number of atoms

{
  "root": {
    "normalizer": string "SystemNormalizer"
    "n_atom_positions": string "8"
    "n_atoms": string "5"
    "event": string "len of atom position does not match number of atoms"
    "proc": string "Entry"
    "process": string "process_entry"
    "process_worker_id": string "nSBSj5gyT2CkhKcmjlnxQ"
    "parser": string "electronicparsers.yambo_parser_entry_point"
    "step": string "SystemNormalizer"
    "logger": string "nomad_processing"
    "timestamp": string "2025-03-25 14:29.21"
    "level": string "ERROR"
  }
}

INFO: electronicparsers.yambo_parser_entry_point | normalizer completed successfully
```


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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters

- * A different system: **CH4**
- * /SAVE/ns.db present

Error: **mismatch** bw *n. of atom coordinates*
and *n. of atoms*

CH4 case: **5** atoms;
n_atoms(C)=1, n_atoms(H)=4
max_n_atoms=4

Yambo:

- * **max_n_atoms**: maximum n. of atoms per chemical species out of all the chemical species present in the investigated system

- * **n_atoms**: n. of atoms of a given chemical species

NOMAD is using *max_n_atoms*
for each chemical species, instead of *n_atoms*!

Error in systems with *different numbers of atoms*
of *different chemical species*!

8 coords

C1	xC1	yC1	zC1
C2	xC2	yC2	zC2
C3	xC3	yC3	zC3
C4	xC4	yC4	zC4
H1	xH1	yH1	zH1
H2	xH2	yH2	zH2
H3	xH3	yH3	zH3
H4	xH4	yH4	zH4

4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters:

→ Our solution:

```

739     )
740     if self.netcdf_parser.mainfile is not None:
741         system = System()
742         run.system.append(system)
743         positions = self.netcdf_parser.get('ATOM_POS', [])
744         max_n_atoms = self.netcdf_parser.get('MAX_ATOMS')
745         n_atoms = self.netcdf_parser.N_ATOMS
746         atom_numbers = np.hstack(
747             [
748                 [self.netcdf_parser.atomic_numbers[int(n)] * int(n_atoms[int(n))]
749                  for n in range(len(n_atoms))]
750             ]
751         )
752
753 # we define the process_and_select function within the parse_input function
754 def process_and_select(positions, max_n_atoms, n_atoms):
755
756     positions = np.array(positions)
757     blocks = []
758     selected = []
759
760     positions = positions.reshape(-1, 3)
761

```

```

762     n_points = positions.shape[0]
763     n_blocks = int( int(n_points) // int(max_n_atoms) )
764

```

```

for i in range(n_blocks):
    start_idx = int(i) * int(max_n_atoms)
    end_idx = (int(i) + 1) * int(max_n_atoms)
    block = positions[start_idx:end_idx]
    blocks.append(block)

```

divide the whole (wrong) list of coordinates into blocks of max_n_atoms lines each (1 block for each chemical species)

```

for i, block in enumerate(blocks):
    n_to_select = int(n_atoms[int(i)])
    selected_from_block = block[:n_to_select]
    for point in selected_from_block:
        selected.append(point)

```

select, for each chemical species, only the first n_atoms lines

```

positions=np.array(selected)

return positions

positions = process_and_select(positions, max_n_atoms, n_atoms)

system.atoms = Atoms(
    positions = positions * ureg.bohr,
    labels=[chemical_symbols[int(n)] for n in atom_numbers],
)

```


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4.5 NOMAD: Yambo cell parameters:

→ Our solution:

```

739 )
740     if self.netcdf_parser:
741         system = System()
742         run.system.applications()
743         positions = self.positions
744         max_n_atoms = self.max_n_atoms
745         n_atoms = self.n_atoms
746         atom_numbers = self.atom_numbers
747         [
748             [self.positions[n],
749              for n in range(n_atoms)]
750         ]
751     )
752
753     # we define the process
754     def process_and_store(
755         positions = self.positions,
756         blocks = [],
757         selected = self.selected,
758         positions = self.positions,
759
760         positions =
761

```

System

section System

sub section system

QUANTITIES

type = molecule / cluster

configuration raw gid = YyCLZOMITTIgX1UiMd9w_8X5UwUp

is representative = true

chemical composition = HHHHC

chemical composition hill = CH4

chemical composition reduced = CH4

SUB SECTIONS

atoms

descriptors

REFERENCED BY closed

Atoms

section Atoms

sub section atoms

○ H

● C

QUANTITIES

species = 5 vector

labels = 5 list

positions = 5 x 3 matrix

lattice vectors = 3 x 3 matrix

lattice vectors reciprocal = 3 x 3 matrix

periodic = 3 list

It works!

We have:

- * added a *test subfolder* in the NOMAD Yambo test folder

- * made a **Pull Request**

<https://github.com/nomad-coe/electronic-parsers/pull/286>

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

(with Hajar Belgroun)

On the general NOMAD:
Example: *R-methyloxirane*

Material

Composition

Chemical formula IUPAC C3H6O	Chemical formula reduced C3H6O
Chemical formula hill C3H6O	Chemical formula descriptive C3H6O
Elements C, H, O	N elements 3 (ternary)

Workflow Graph

No task to show

Entry
section [EntryArchive](#)

SUB SECTIONS

results

metadata

workflow2

run

REFERENCED BY [closed](#)

Run
section [Run](#)

sub section [run](#)

SUB SECTIONS

program

time run

method

system

calculation

REFERENCED BY [closed](#)

Calculation
section [Calculation](#)

sub section [calculation](#)

SUB SECTIONS

energy

eigenvalues

REFERENCED BY [closed](#)

For other codes:

* Run → Calculation → Spectra
and/or

* Results → Properties → Spectroscopic → Spectra

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

* in the “general” part: `~/nomad/datamodel/results.py`:

```
class Spectra(MSection):
    m_def = Section(
        description="""
        Base class for Spectra calculation information as obtained from an experiment or a computation.
        """
    )
    type = Quantity(
        type=MEnum(
            'EELS',
            'XAS',
            'XANES',
            'EXAFS',
            'XES',
            'XPS',
            'RXIS',
            'Polarizability',
            'Dielectric function',
            config.services.unavailable_value,
        ),
    )
```

Added these 2
Spectra types

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

* in the Yambo parser:

```
def init_quantities(self):
    re_f = r'[-+]*\d*\.\d+[Ee]*[-+]*\d*'
```

```
self._quantities = [
    Quantity(
```

Spectrum type, read from uploaded o* file

```
Quantity(
    'sp type',
    r'(EELS|Polarizability|Absorption)',
    repeats=False,
),
```

```
def to_values(block):
    values = []
    names = []
    for line in block.strip().splitlines():
        if line.startswith('# E/ev[1]'):
            names = [k.strip() for k in line.split() if k != '#']
            continue
        if names and not line.startswith('#'):
            values.append(line.split())
    values = np.array(values, dtype=np.float64)
    return values
```

To identify the header of the part which contains the spectrum

1) we can have several o* files in a single upload

```
spectra_files = [ sp_file for sp_file in os.listdir(self.mainfile_parser.maindir) if sp_file.startswith('o*') ]
```

```
for spectra_file in spectra_files:
    self.mainfile_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(self.mainfile_parser.maindir, spectra_file)
    if self.mainfile_parser.sp_type is not None:
```

```
spectra = Spectra()
calc.spectra.append(spectra)

if self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type') == 'Absorption':
    spectra.type = 'Dielectric function'
else:
    spectra.type = self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type')
with open(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile) as f:
    spectra_file_content = f.read()

output_spectra_values = to_values(spectra_file_content)

spectra.n_energies = output_spectra_values.shape[0]
spectra.excitation_energies = output_spectra_values[:, 0]
spectra.intensities = output_spectra_values[:, 1]
```

Entry files

folder

- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.CD_q1_IP
- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.Esort_q1_IP
- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.alpha_q1_IP
- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.eel_q1_IP
- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.eps_q1_IP
- o-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.jdos_q1_IP
- r-TrpTyr4_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br... electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point
- r_setup electronicparsers:yambo_parser_entry_point
- yambo_absdic_y23nov_500b_newdip_br0.05_4000pts.in

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

* in the Yambo parser:

```
def init_quantities(self):
    re_f = r'[-+]*\d*\.\d+[Ee]*[-+]*\d*'
```

```
self._quantities = [
    Quantity(
```

Spectrum type,
read from
uploaded o* file

```
Quantity(
    'sp type',
    r'(EELS|Polarizability|Absorption)',
    repeats=False,
),
```

```
def to_values(block):
    values = []
    names = []
    for line in block.strip().splitlines():
        if line.startswith('# E/ev[1]'):
            names = [k.strip() for k in line.split() if k != '#']
            continue
        if names and not line.startswith('#'):
            values.append(line.split())
    values = np.array(values, dtype=np.float64)
    return values
```

```
spectra_files = [ sp_file for sp_file in os.listdir(self.mainfile_parser.maindir) if sp_file.startswith('o')]
for spectra_file in spectra_files:
```

```
self.mainfile_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(self.mainfile_parser.maindir, spectra_file)
if self.mainfile_parser.sp_type is not None:
```

2) Not all o* files
are spectra files

```
spectra = Spectra()
calc.spectra.append(spectra)

if self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type') == 'Absorption':
    spectra.type = 'Dielectric function'
else:
    spectra.type = self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type')
with open(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile) as f:
    spectra_file_content = f.read()

output_spectra_values = to_values(spectra_file_content)

spectra.n_energies = output_spectra_values.shape[0]
spectra.excitation_energies = output_spectra_values[:, 0]
spectra.intensities = output_spectra_values[:, 1]
```


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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

* in the Yambo parser:

```
def init_quantities(self):
    re_f = r'[-+]*\d*\.\d+[Ee]*[-+]*\d*'
```

```
self._quantities = [
    Quantity(
```

Spectrum type,
read from
uploaded o* file

```
Quantity(
    'sp_type',
    r'(EELS|Polarizability|Absorption)',
    repeats=False,
),
```

```
def to_values(block):
    values = []
    names = []
    for line in block.strip().splitlines():
        if line.startswith('# E/ev[1]'):
            names = [k.strip() for k in line.split() if k != '#']
            continue
        if names and not line.startswith('#'):
            values.append(line.split())
    values = np.array(values, dtype=np.float64)
    return values
```

```
spectra_files = [ sp_file for sp_file in os.listdir(self.mainfile_parser.maindir) if sp_file.startswith('o')]

for spectra_file in spectra_files:
    self.mainfile_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(self.mainfile_parser.maindir, spectra_file)
    if self.mainfile_parser.sp_type is not None:

        spectra = Spectra()

        calc.spectra.append(spectra)

        if self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type') == 'Absorption':
            spectra.type = 'Dielectric function'
        else:
            spectra.type = self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type')
        with open(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile) as f:
            spectra_file_content = f.read()

        output_spectra_values = to_values(spectra_file_content)

        spectra.n_energies = output_spectra_values.shape[0]
        spectra.excitation_energies = output_spectra_values[:, 0]
        spectra.intensities = output_spectra_values[:, 1]
```

3) sp_type from file;
Spectra.type as defined
in the "Spectra" class
in the general part

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

* in the Yambo parser:

```
def init_quantities(self):
    re_f = r'[-+]*\d*\.\d+[Ee]*[-+]*\d*'
```

```
self._quantities = [
    Quantity(
```

Spectrum type, read from uploaded o* file

```
Quantity(
    'sp type',
    r'(EELS|Polarizability|Absorption)',
    repeats=False,
),
```

```
def to_values(block):
    values = []
    names = []
    for line in block.strip().splitlines():
        if line.startswith('# E/ev[1]'):
            names = [k.strip() for k in line.split() if k != '#']
            continue
        if names and not line.startswith('#'):
            values.append(line.split())
    values = np.array(values, dtype=np.float64)
    return values
```

```
spectra_files = [ sp_file for sp_file in os.listdir(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile)
                  if sp_file.endswith('.o*') ]

for spectra_file in spectra_files:
    self.mainfile_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile, spectra_file)
    if self.mainfile_parser.sp_type is not None:
        spectra = Spectra()
        calc.spectra.append(spectra)

    if self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type') == 'Absorption':
        spectra.type = 'Dielectric function'
    else:
        spectra.type = self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type')
    with open(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile) as f:
        spectra_file_content = f.read()
```

```
output_spectra_values = to_values(spectra_file_content)

spectra.n_energies = output_spectra_values.shape[0]
spectra.excitation_energies = output_spectra_values[:, 0]
spectra.intensities = output_spectra_values[:, 1]
```

#	# E/ev[1]	ALPHA-Im[2]	ALPHA-Re[3]
#	0.00000000	0.00000000	308.198151
#	0.500125019E-2	0.228705769E-2	308.198151
#	0.100025004E-1	0.457405765E-2	308.198761
#	0.150037510E-1	0.686115585E-2	308.199371
#	0.200050008E-1	0.914823171E-2	308.199677
#	0.250062495E-1	0.114355730E-1	308.200897
#	0.300075021E-1	0.137228062E-1	308.202423
#	0.350087509E-1	0.160101634E-1	308.203613
#	0.400100015E-1	0.182976108E-1	308.205750
#	0.450112484E-1	0.205852333E-1	308.207275
#	0.500124991E-1	0.228730571E-1	308.209381

Relevant columns

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Our implementation:

Example 1:

R-methyloxirane:

* 1 spectrum only

* 5 columns

4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

The screenshot shows the NOMAD interface with the following structure:

- Entry**
 - section EntryArchive
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - results
 - metadata
 - workflow2
 - run**
- Run**
 - section Run
 - sub section run
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - program
 - time run
 - method
 - system
 - calculation**
- Calculation**
 - section Calculation
 - sub section calculation
 - SUB SECTIONS
 - energy
 - eigenvalues
 - spectra**
 - REFERENCED BY: closed
- Spectra**
 - section Spectra
 - sub section spectra
 - QUANTITIES
 - type = Polarizability
 - n energies = 4000
 - excitation energies = 4000 vector
 - intensities = 4000 vector
 - REFERENCED BY: closed

Spectroscopic properties

Polarizability → spectra.type

#	E/ev[1]	ALPHA-Im[2]	ALPHA-Re[3]	ALPHAO-Im[4]	ALPHAO-Re[5]
#	0.00000000	-0.656836937E-5	17.2148304	0.00000000	54.6610031
#	0.250062509E-2	0.421063596E-4	17.2148361	0.138719348E-3	54.6609955
#	0.500125019E-2	0.907705107E-4	17.2148380	0.277411513E-3	54.6609955
#	0.750187552E-2	0.139449287E-3	17.2148457	0.416129275E-3	54.6610260
#	0.100025004E-1	0.188115082E-3	17.2148552	0.554818194E-3	54.6610451
#	0.125031248E-1	0.236791151E-3	17.2148666	0.693545968E-3	54.6610794
#	0.150037510E-1	0.285461807E-3	17.2148781	0.832231832E-3	54.6611328
#	0.175043754E-1	0.334140612E-3	17.2148933	0.970952329E-3	54.6611557
#	0.200050008E-1	0.382807455E-3	17.2149124	0.110964430E-2	54.6612129

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

Example 2: **TrpTyr dipeptide:**

* 3 different spectra (**EELS, Polarizability, Dielectric Function**)

* 3 columns

The screenshot displays the NOMAD interface for a Yambo calculation. The 'Entry' panel shows the 'run' sub-section. The 'Run' panel shows the 'method' sub-section. The 'Calculation' panel shows the 'spectra' sub-section with 'EELS', 'Polarizability', and 'Dielectric function' selected. The 'Spectra' panel shows 'type = Polarizability', 'n energies = 4000', and 'excitation energies = 4000 vector'. The 'Intensities' panel shows a table of values for the 'intensities = 4000 vector'.

#	E/ev[1]	ALPHA-Im[2]	ALPHA-Re[3]
#	0.00000000	0.00000000	308.198151
#	0.500125019E-2	0.228705769E-2	308.198151
#	0.100025004E-1	0.457405765E-2	308.198761
#	0.150037510E-1	0.686115585E-2	308.199371
#	0.200050008E-1	0.914823171E-2	308.199677
#	0.250062495E-1	0.114355730E-1	308.200897
#	0.300075021E-1	0.137228062E-1	308.202423
#	0.350087509E-1	0.160101634E-1	308.203613

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Our implementation:

Example 2: **TrpTyr dipeptide**:

* 3 different spectra (EELS, Polarizability, Dielectric Function)

* 3 columns

4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Spectroscopic properties

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Our implementation:

Example 2: **TrpTyr dipeptide:**

* 3 different spectra (EELS, Polarizability, Dielectric Function)

* 3 columns

4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Spectroscopic properties


```
spectra_files = [ sp_file for sp_file in os.listdir(self.mainfile_parser.maindir) if sp_file.startswith('o')]

for spectra_file in spectra_files:
    self.mainfile_parser.mainfile = os.path.join(self.mainfile_parser.maindir, spectra_file)
    if self.mainfile_parser.sp_type is not None:

        spectra = Spectra()
        calc.spectra.append(spectra)

        if self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type') == 'Absorption':
            spectra.type = 'Dielectric function'
        else:
            spectra.type = self.mainfile_parser.get('sp_type')
        with open(self.mainfile_parser.mainfile) as f:
            spectra_file_content = f.read()

        output_spectra_values = to_values(spectra_file_content)

        spectra.n_energies = output_spectra_values.shape[0]
        spectra.excitation_energies = output_spectra_values[:, 0]
        spectra.intensities = output_spectra_values[:, 1]
```

Recognizing spectra types is needed in order to obtain separate plots (not only for having the correct plot labels)

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4.6 NOMAD: Yambo spectra

Our implementation:

→ We have made a **Pull Request**:

* <https://github.com/Jajar26/electronic-parsers/pull/1>

--> PR about our changes in the yambo parser and metainfo

* <https://github.com/nomad-coe/nomad/issues>

→ created an “issue” about the needed changes in the general part

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4.7 NOMAD: Siesta: DOS and band str.

General NOMAD: **Siesta**:

- * no density of states (DOS) plots
- * no band structure plots

Our implementation (Masoumeh Alihosseini):
Start from DOS parsing for *FHlaims* and *Exciting* codes

(with Masoumeh Alihosseini,
UNIMI postdoc)

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4.7 NOMAD: Siesta: DOS

General NOMAD:

- * no DOS plots
- * no band str. plots

Our implementation

```
def parse_calculation(source):
    sec_calc = Calculation()
    sec_run.calculation.append(sec_calc)
    sec_system = parse_system(source)
    sec_run.calculation[-1]
    nspin = self.out_parser.get('nspin', 1)
    print("Found spin channels:", nspin)
    fermi = self.out_parser.get('fermi_energy')
    print("DEBUG - Fermi parsed from output:", fermi)

    if not sec_system.atoms and self.out_parser.get('x_siesta_number_of_atoms'):
        n_atoms = self.out_parser.get('x_siesta_number_of_atoms')
        sec_system.atoms = Atoms(
            labels=['X'] * n_atoms,
            positions=[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0]] * n_atoms
        )

    sec_calc.system_ref = sec_system

    dos = Dos()
    if nspin == 2:
        dos.spin_polarized = True
        dos_path = os.path.join(self.maindir, "dos")
        if os.path.exists(dos_path):
            try:
                data = np.loadtxt(dos_path)
            except Exception as e:
                self.logger.warning(f"Could not read DOS file: {e}")
                return
            if data.shape[1] < 4:
                self.logger.warning(f"DOS file {dos_file} does not have 4 colum
                return

        energies = data[:, 0]
        dos_up = data[:, 1]
        dos_down = data[:, 2]
        dos_total = data[:, 3]
```

```
# spin-up
sec_dos_up = Dos()
sec_dos_up.spin_channel = 0
sec_dos_up.energies = energies * ureg.eV
sec_dos_val_up = DosValues(value=dos_up / ureg.eV)
sec_dos_up.total = [sec_dos_val_up]
sec_run.calculation[-1].dos_electronic.append(sec_dos_up)

# spin-down
sec_dos_down = Dos()
sec_dos_down.spin_channel = 1
sec_dos_down.energies = energies * ureg.eV
sec_dos_val_down = DosValues(value=dos_down / ureg.eV)
sec_dos_down.total = [sec_dos_val_down]
sec_run.calculation[-1].dos_electronic.append(sec_dos_down)

# total
sec_dos_total = Dos()
sec_dos_total.energies = energies * ureg.eV
sec_dos_val_total = DosValues(value=dos_total / ureg.eV)
sec_dos_total.total = [sec_dos_val_total]
sec_run.calculation[-1].dos_electronic.append(sec_dos_total)
```

```
elif nspin == 1:
    dos_path = os.path.join(self.maindir, "dos")
    if os.path.exists(dos_path):
        try:
            data = np.loadtxt(dos_path)
        except Exception as e:
            self.logger.warning(f"Could not read DOS file: {e}")
            return

    if data.shape[1] < 2:
        self.logger.warning("DOS file does not have at least 2 columns (energy, total)")
        return

    energies = data[:, 0]
    dos_total = data[:, 1]

    sec_dos_total = Dos()
    sec_dos_total.energies = energies * ureg.eV
    sec_dos_total.spin_polarized = False
    sec_dos_val_total = DosValues(value=dos_total / ureg.eV)
    sec_dos_total.total = [sec_dos_val_total]

    sec_run.calculation[-1].dos_electronic = [sec_dos_total]
```


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4.7 NOMAD: Siesta: DOS and band str.

With our implementation:

- * **DOS** correctly plotted
- * however, E_F not found/used
- * **band str.** parsing still in progress:
plots band str; k-point labels still missing
(based both on Masoumeh's implementation
for Siesta DOS and on band str
implementations for other codes
(VASP, or QE by N. Daelman))

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5 Conclusions and Perspectives

DONE:

- * Data Management Plans (DMP) and Interactive Remote Access (IRA) forms
- * installed a “personal” Oasis (+ group Oasis installed by IT team: still to be finalized: creating users, how to have (admin) CLI access...)
- * NOMAD dissemination / hands-on meetings for UMIL Theo&Sim colleagues

* NOMAD:

- **Yambo cell params, atom coords etc:**
solved n atoms / n coords mismatch error
- **Yambo spectra**
- Siesta: DOS plots, band str plots
- QE band str. (FAIRmat team with our contrib.)

Yambo GW error (FAIRmat team with our contrib.)

TO DO:

- * completing the setup of the UMIL Theo&Sim group Oasis
- * further NOMAD / FAIR / ... dissemination meetings
- * **NOMAD:**
 - Siesta: completing band str implem.
 - Yambo GW: plot GW-corrected band str?
 - LAMMPS

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

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Thank...

- **you all for your attention**
- **Simona Achilli (UMIL), Tommaso Rodani, Matteo Biagetti**
- **Hajar Belgroun and Masoumeh Alihosseini (UMIL)**
- **FAIRmat team**
- **organizers, teachers, tutors for this MDMC course**
- **fellow MDMC participants for discussions**

Nano Foundries
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This Pilot training activity has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU within the project PNRR "PRP@CERIC" IR0000028 and «NFFA-DI" IR0000015 - Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, "Fondo per la realizzazione di un sistema integrato di infrastrutture di ricerca e innovazione" - Azione 3.1.1, "Creazione di nuove IR o potenziamento di quelle esistenti che concorrono agli obiettivi di Eccellenza Scientifica di Horizon Europe e costituzione di reti".